

RARE ANIMALS ARE UNDER CONSTANT CONTROL IN THE CENTRAL KYZYLKUM NATIONAL NATURE PARK

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Abstract: In the article, the Central Kyzylkum National Nature Park was established in order to preserve the diversity of the animal world, and it is about the important role of protecting the unique and endangered animals, saving and breeding of those that are in danger of extinction. the idea goes.

Key words: wildlife, camera trap, climate, fauna, Turkmen caracal.

Introduction. In the Uchkuduq district of the Navoi region, the national nature park "Central Kyzylkum" with a total area of 1,200,000 hectares was established. Various measures are being implemented in our country in order to preserve endangered animal and plant species, to establish ecological stability, to increase the number of rare and endangered species, to expand specially protected areas and to bring them under state protection.

The territories of the "Central Kyzylkum" National Nature Park established in this regard are very important and have a rich biodiversity. The National Nature Park protects unique natural complexes and objects, as well as rare animals and birds under the threat of extinction, as well as plant species and landscapes there. As a result of the establishment of the activity of the National Nature Park, the work of bringing, installing and providing technical support of photo traps in order to effectively organize the work process and identify the diversity of the animal world continues.

Fig. 1. Control raid activities by scientific staff and inspectors and the process of installing photo traps

In order to protect the rare species of animals and plants in the "Central Kyzylkum" National Nature Park, state inspectors are carrying out round-the-clock control raids.

Fig. 2. A Turkmen blackbird captured in a photo trap

The Turkmen caracal (*Caracal caracal* spp. *Michaelis*) became the prey of one of the photo traps installed in the Kupit section of the "Central Kyzylkum" National Nature Park under the Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection and Climate Change.

Caracal (*Felis caracal*) is an animal belonging to the cat family. The body length is 65-82 cm, the tail is 25-30 cm, the weight is 11-13 kg, but its body is thin. There are small black markings on the beak and ears. The tips of the ears are covered with long hairs. Because of these long feathers, the caracal is sometimes called the desert lynx. The claws have coarse hairs that form a pad, which makes it easier to move on sandy soil.

Caracal region - the deserts of southern Turkmenistan, along the shores of the Caspian Sea, the arid mountainous regions of Africa, the Mediterranean Sea, the Near East and then to India. The main activity of this cat occurs at night, but in winter and spring it also appears during the day. It hides in the holes of pigs and foxes, occupying them for several years in a row.

Caracal prefers to search and chase a wounded animal. Since it cannot run at high speed for a long time, it does not hunt with weight, but hides from its prey and overtakes it in ambush for a short distance with a large jump. Thus, he can catch even a fast tolay rabbit. The caracal has such a quick reaction that it can catch several birds, even a bird in flight, and its height

Able to jump up to 2 meters. The main food is rodents, hares, rarely small antelopes. Caracal also feeds on hedgehogs, insects, and reptiles. If he settles near villages, he can hunt birds, attack lambs. The breeding season is in early April. They grow slowly.

The following subspecies of caracal are known:

Caracal (*Felis*) *caracal caracal* - Lives in Sudan and South Africa.

Caracal (*Felis*) *caracal algira* - Lives in North Africa.

Caracal (*Felis*) *Caracal damarensis* - Lives in Namibia.

Caracal (*Felis*) *Caracal limpopoensis* - Located in Botswana.

Caracal (*Felis*) *caracal lucani* - Common in Gabon.

Caracal (*Felis*) *caracal michaelis* - Lives in Turkmenistan.

Caracal (*Felis*) *caracal nubicus* - Found in Sudan and Ethiopia.

Caracal (*Felis*) *Caracal poecilictis* - Lives in Nigeria.

Caracal (*Felis*) *caracal schmitzi* - Widespread from Arabia to India.

Turkmen caracal (*Felis caracal michaelis*) is a subspecies of caracal. The length of the body is 73-82 cm, the tail of the male is 21.4 - 32.0 cm, the height of the ear is 7.5-9.0 cm, the weight of the male is 11.5-12.7 kg, the female is 8-9 kg. the color of the back, sides, limbs and tail is solid sandy yellow, covered with strong gray hairs. The throat, sides of the belly and the inside of the legs are white. The ears on the back are black with gray hairs. On top of the ears there are black elastic hairs up to 6 cm long, the fur is short in winter and summer. Claws adapted to move on sand. The legs are long and the front is about 4-6 cm shorter than the back, the tracks are large, round, and there are no claw marks.

Turkmen Karakalpakstan live in the Arol hills and fortified sands covered with saxovul, juzgun, tarak and other bushes. He often hunts during the day in winter and at night in summer. In spring and autumn, it is found both at night and during the day. The breeding season takes place in January-February. Pregnancy lasts an average of 70 days. They can give birth to one to six kittens. Kittens appear in the first half of April-May. At first, their eyes are closed, after 7-8 days their eyes begin to open, they grow quickly. At the age of 3 weeks they start walking, at the age of 2 months they hunt rodents with their parents, at the age of 4 months - independently. By the end of autumn, they are slightly smaller than adults. At the age of 10-11 months, kittens reach adult size.

Caracal's enemy is a wolf, competitors for food - a fox and spotted cat, and in some places - a jackal. Due to the small number of caracals, there is no intense relationship with other predators.

Currently, due to their reduced number, hunting is prohibited and the Turkmen caracal is included in the IUCN Red Book. In the territory of the National Nature Park, their habitat, reproduction and hunting by poachers are controlled.

Conclusion. Thus, it is necessary to protect the surrounding environment and the animal world, to convey it to the next generation in its entirety, and it should be the main goal of every employee. As a result of the creation of the "Central Kyzylkum" National Nature Park, the number of animals will increase, and the distribution areas of plant populations will be expanded as a result of the protection of rare animals and plants and natural complexes in the protected natural areas. In this regard, the staff of the National Nature Reserve of the Central Kyzylkum are conducting round-the-clock control work.

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